

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MOODS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The following article discusses the ways and problems of expressing moods of the verb, their categories analyzing them between English and Uzbek language. In particular, the article identifies different approaches to the semantic classification of sentences of the moods in both languages.

Keywords: category of the mood, imperative mood, subjunctive mood, Indicative mood, conditional mood, oblique mood, analytical form of mood

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Introduction: Each language has its own rules, differences and have similarities. In this article, we will briefly describe the verb moods in two families and more broadly about the imperative mood.

Verb Moods are ways of looking at verbs and classifying them which show the attitude of the speaker. Verb moods are classifications that indicate the attitude of the speaker. Each language may have its own moods. Yet their types or numbers can be different or similar .

There are basically three types of moods of the verb in English language, and they are as follows.

4. Indicative- The indicative mood is used in most statements and questions to assert or show (i.e. indicate) something.

Example: They feel sad.

5. Imperative- The imperative mood is used to expresses commands or requests.

Example: Look at me !

6. Subjunctive- The subjunctive mood is used to express a subjective opinion and to make contrary-to-fact or hypothetical statements.

Example: If I were queen (but I'm not) [1]

The category of mood expresses the relations between the action and reality from the speaker's point of view. He can treat it as real, unreal, probable or as a kind of inducement. Hence, we traditionally differentiate 3 principal types of mood in English: the indicative, the imperative and the oblique moods. The number and

types of concrete mood forms can vary with different authors, because of the variety of verb forms, their homonymy on the plane of expression and difference on the plane of content.

The indicative mood-presents an action or event as a real fact from the grammatical point of view. The verb in this mood form strictly distinguishes the tense category, because it names actions taking place in the objective time: present, past or future.

The imperative mood- expresses an inducement, addressed by the speaker to the addressee. The peculiarity of this mood-form is that it does not distinguish tense, aspect and voice categories. It is used only in actual intercourse and so it coincides with the moment of speaking. Hence, it always has the form of the present tense. Example: Stay here! Don't go there.

However, taking into consideration the meaning of the imperative mood, we can also refer to its field some interrogative sentences which actually express not a question, but a request or a mild command. The predicate verb-form in such sentences coincides with the indicative mood in such cases. Example: Will you open the door? - mild command. Shall I do it now?

Modal verbs with an infinitive can be used in the imperative mood to express a request, a permission, a prohibition or an order. Example: You may go now. You mustn't stay here too. You are to come at ten.

Some authors speak of the word combination with "let" as an analytical form of the Imperative Mood. Semantically such constructions can express an inducement. This inducement is addressed to the 1st person or to the 3rd person (Let me stay, let him stay) and in the last case it is not direct. When treating this construction with "let" as an analytical form of the Imperative Mood, the component "let" is treated as an auxiliary element. It is true that in some cases "let" happens to be considerably devoid of its lexical meaning. Example: Let's do it now! Let him stay here!

However, it is difficult to agree to the idea that constructions with "let" are analytical forms of the Imperative Mood. We can give the following arguments: The pronoun or noun is an object to "let" and so there are syntactic relations between the noun and pronoun what is foreign to analytical forms. We can find secondary predicative relations between the noun or pronoun and the infinitive which follows it, thus making up a CO construction, what is foreign to analytical forms. Example: Let me help you.

The component "let" can hardly be a pure auxiliary element, as in negative and interrogative forms it takes an auxiliary itself. In addition to that, when transformed into a declarative sentence it becomes the predicate and takes a

subject. Hence, the pronoun or noun after “let” can’t be the subject of “let” as some authors think.

e.g. Will you let me do it? Don’t let us stay here. She never lets me stay there after ten.

So the word combinations with “let” can be treated as a means of expressing the meaning of the Imperative Mood, but it is not an analytical form. The imperative mood is formed by the infinitive without the particle “to”, but unlike the infinitive it takes the auxiliary in the negative and interrogative forms: Example: Don’t forget it. I want not to forget it.

When treating Oblique Moods we can say that it is one of disputable questions in English grammar. Different authors speak of different types and number of oblique moods. Oblique moods denote unreal or problematic actions and so they can’t express objective time and do not distinguish tense-forms like the Indicative Mood. Oblique Moods denote only relative time relations, that is simultaneity and futurity as one time-plane and priority as the other time-plane.[2]

- Indicative: He came there. The sun rises in the East;

- Imperative: Read the letter! Go there!

- Subjunctive I: (be/go for all persons) I suggest that he/you go there. If it be so;

- Subjunctive II: (were for all persons, and forms knew, had known homonymous with forms of Past Tense, Perfect and Non-Perfect Phase) I wish I were present. If I knew... If I had known...;

- Suppositional: (analytical forms should/would + infinitive) Should you meet him, tell him to come. I suggest that he/you should go there;

- Conditional: (analytical forms should/would + infinitive in the main clause of unreal condition sentences) What would you answer if you were asked?

Now we will compare and analyze the moods in the Uzbek and English languages:

A command (imperative) is a desire- about the execution or non-execution of work action order, wish, request, request, advice expresses meanings. Now let's talk about the moods of the verb in Uzbek language:

There are four types of moods of the verb in Uzbek language:

5. Indicative mood (execution intent)
6. Imperative mood
7. Subjunctive mood
8. Conditional mood

Imperative mood(Command-desire) - a form of the verb expressing the meaning of command, desire, request, advice to perform or not perform an action or situation. It means to call for an action. The imperative of the verb means that the speaker commands, urges, urges to perform an action, and each subtlety of

meaning is characterized by its own tone. For example: Beat your blood. Live. Laugh, happy generations of our time. Go faster, dear friend. Imperative forms are formed by adding the following suffixes to verb bases: - (a) y, - (a) yin, -gin, - (i) ng, - (i) ngizlar, -sin, - (sinlar)

Suffixes of imperative mood				
	Singular		Plural	
I Person	-y, -ay	o'qiy, boray	-ylik, -aylik	O'qiylik, boraylik
II Person	-gin, (-gil)	Borgin, borgil	-ing, -ingiz	boring, boringiz
III Person	-sin	borsin	-sinlar	borsinlar

The motivation of the speaker to perform the action is directed directly to the II person. Therefore, the main form of the imperative is the singular and plural form of the second person: Qadr donim, tezroq buyoqqa kel. Odamlar, ona tabiatni asrang. (- My dear, come here quickly. People, save the mother nature)–

The singular form of the second person of the imperative mood has three forms:

1. Strict command, the main form in which the command of imperative is understood: This form has no-suffix: Kitobim niber. Yangilikni bizga ham ayt. (Give me my book. Tell us the news too). In this form, the meaning of request, request, advice is also expressed: Qani yur, nutqingni sal pishitib ol. U shaharga bormoqchi emas. Sen o'zing yaxshilab tushuntir.

2. It is formed by adding the suffix -gin (-gil) to the base of the verb. This form expresses the meaning of a command in the form of a request, a request, an advice. For example: Menikutgilva men qaytaman. Kitobingni bir pasga berib turingin.

3. It is formed by adding the suffix -(ing) to the base of the verb. Respect for one person is sometimes expressed in the plural of the second person: Yuqori marralarni ko'zlayvering, Umidjon. Yigitlar, hammangiz ishga bel bog'lang.

The II person plural form of the imperative mood is mainly formed in two ways:

1. By adding the suffix -(i)nglar to the base of the verb: Qani o'g'illarim, biroz dam olinglar.

2. By adding the suffix -(i)ngiz to the base of the verb: Do'stlar, ishonch bilan kutingiz bizni. Hech qachon bizlardan umid uzmingiz.

In the III person form of the imperative, the meanings of command, request, and encouragement are conveyed by means, that is, they are directed to person and things that did not participate in the conversation through the II person, without being directed directly to the III person. For example: Uyiga javob berish kerak, o'n besh-yigirma kunga borib kelsin. Dasta-dasta gular keltirsin, sho'x va quvnoq do'stlarga buyur.

The III person singular of the imperative is formed by adding the suffix -sin to the base of the verb, and the plural form is formed by adding the suffix -lar to the

singular form: *kelsin-kelsinlar, yozsin-yozsinlar*. For example: *Ayting, kirsin. Ilimos, ular bugun oquyga o'tsinlar*.

III person form also means a solemn call, a strict command: *Bu vazifani bajarish I kurs talabalariga yuklatilsin*.

The speaker cannot give orders directly to himself. Therefore, in the I person of the imperative mood, there is a desire, a desire to perform an action, the meanings of an agreement, or an urge to perform an action together with the participation of the speaker himself. The I person singular of the imperative is formed by adding the suffix *-y(-ay)* to the base of the verb: *yoza^y, o'qiy^y, boray^y, ishlay^y*.. To emphasize, add *-in* to strengthen the meaning. *-in* is added and an expanded form is formed, such as *oqi-yin, bor-ay-in, yoz-ayin, ishla-yin*. *Chevarqiz deb maqtay - Chevarqiz deb maqtayin*.

The plural form of the I person is formed by adding the suffix *-lik* to the singular form of this person: *o'qiy- o'qiylik, yozay-yozaylik*, for example. In the plural form - to urge to perform an action by several persons in which the speaker is also involved, and at the same time the desire of the first person is also expressed as: *Hali dalada boshlangan gapni davom ettiraylik*.

Remember: The part of the verb without tense, the category of number is II person expresses imperative, command-desire, tendency. For example: *Don't run over an untried horse. Akangizni chaqiring, bugungi faoliyati uchun javob bersin*.

It is also possible to add the suffix *-gin* to this part to strengthen the imperative meaning, so these two forms are considered synonymous: *ko'r, ko'rgin*. For example: *Qo'lingni ochiq tutgin, boshingni g'oz tutgin*.

Very important: Imperative adverbs differ from other verb adverbs in that they can express three grammatical meanings in Uzbek at once. For example, the verb *bor-ay* has one grammatical form, i.e. suffix: *-ay*; and the grammatical meaning is three: imperative-desire mood (mood meaning), future tense (tense meaning), I person singular (person-number meaning).

As you can see, the Uzbek language has these moods of the verb. Each verb mood has its own rules and affixes that give meaning to words when used in a sentence and depending on their function.¹³⁵

In both languages the Indicative mood represents an action as a fact: *He is here - U shu yerda, He said so - U shunday dedi*.

The Imperative mood expresses the speaker's inducement (order, request, command, and the like) addressed to another person to do something: *Come here - Kelingiz, Wake up - Turingiz*¹³⁶

Conclusion. In summary, we would like to point out that modality is a notional category which expresses the relation of the utterance to reality. Both

¹³⁵2010-2018 issues of "Language and Literature Education" magazine

¹³⁶Hajiyev A. Uzbek word formation system. - Tashkent: Teacher, 2007

languages have verb tenses, moods of the verb and they have their own functions. In the Uzbek language, there are four verb conjugations, each of which has its own suffix. In English, there are mainly three verb moods, and they give meaning to sentences depending on their functions.

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